

Moderating Effect of Risk Management Committee on Ownership Structure and Sustainability Reporting of Listed Non-Financial Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the moderating effect of risk management committees on the relationship between ownership structures and sustainability reporting among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Using data from 91 non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) between 2019 and 2023, the research employs a fixed-effects panel regression analysis to evaluate the impact of managerial ownership and foreign ownership on sustainability disclosures. The findings reveal significant positive relationships between managerial ownership, foreign ownership, and sustainability reporting, highlighting the critical role of these ownership structures in enhancing corporate transparency and accountability. However, the study finds that the moderating effect of risk management committees is complex, with managerial representation within these committees showing a significant positive influence on sustainability disclosures, whereas foreign representation appears to have no significant impact. These results underscore the importance of effective governance mechanisms, particularly diverse and active risk management committees, in promoting sustainability practices. The study concludes that ownership structures and risk management committees play pivotal roles in influencing sustainability reporting among non-financial firms in Nigeria and recommends strengthening governance frameworks to optimize transparency and accountability in sustainability disclosures. This research contributes to the broader discourse on corporate governance and sustainability in emerging economies, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to enhance sustainability reporting practices.

Keywords: Foreign ownership, Non-financial, Managerial ownership, Risk management committee; Sustainability reporting

1. Introduction

Sustainability reporting has become a vital component of modern business strategy as stakeholders increasingly demand transparency regarding a firm's environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices. This reporting allows organizations to communicate their commitment to sustainable development and responsible governance, fostering trust among investors, customers, and regulators (Eccles et al., 2014; KPMG, 2020). The necessity of sustainability reporting is underscored by global trends emphasizing corporate accountability and the need for businesses to mitigate risks associated with climate change

and social inequality (Ioannou & Serafeim, 2017). Companies that engage in comprehensive sustainability reporting often experience enhanced reputational value, improved risk management, and better long-term financial performance (Sullivan & Mackenzie, 2017; Velte, 2019).

Ownership structure plays a critical role in shaping corporate governance and influencing strategic decisions in today's business environment. The distribution of ownership among different stakeholders can affect a firm's commitment to sustainability practices, with varying impacts based on whether ownership is concentrated among insiders or diversified among external investors (La Porta et al., 1999; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). A well-structured ownership framework can encourage responsible management practices and enhance stakeholder engagement, ultimately leading to improved sustainability outcomes (Agle et al., 2006; Miller & Triana, 2009; Oyedokun, & Amafa, 2022). Thus, understanding ownership structures is essential for assessing their implications on corporate sustainability initiatives.

The establishment of a Risk Management Committee (RMC) is increasingly recognized as crucial for effective governance in the corporate landscape. These committees are responsible for overseeing risk management strategies and ensuring that firms are well-equipped to handle potential threats, thereby enhancing their resilience and sustainability (Gonzalez et al., 2020; McCarthy & Latham, 2018). An RMC facilitates informed decision-making processes, promoting a culture of risk awareness that can significantly impact sustainability reporting practices (Harrison et al., 2014; Olsson et al., 2018; Ajibade, Oyedokun, & Onibiyo, 2018). Consequently, the role of an RMC becomes even more relevant in the context of ownership structures, as its presence may moderate the relationship between ownership and sustainability disclosures.

The empirical relationship between ownership structure and sustainability reporting has garnered considerable attention in the literature. Research suggests that different ownership types influence sustainability practices in distinct ways, impacting firms' motivations and capacities to engage in sustainability reporting (Bai et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2015). Specifically, managerial ownership may encourage transparency in reporting due to aligned interests, while foreign ownership can introduce different governance norms that influence sustainability practices (Zhou et al., 2020; O'Brien & Van Duren, 2021). Understanding these dynamics is essential for advancing the discourse on corporate governance and sustainability.

Examining the relationship between ownership structure proxies and sustainability proxies reveals significant insights into how different ownership forms affect various dimensions of sustainability disclosure. For instance, studies indicate that managerial ownership is positively associated with Environmental Disclosure due to management's vested interest in long-term sustainability (Hussainey et al., 2011). Conversely, foreign ownership may lead to enhanced Social Disclosure as foreign investors often expect high standards of corporate social responsibility (Hossain et al., 2016). By dissecting these relationships, we can gain a more nuanced understanding of how ownership structures influence specific aspects of sustainability reporting.

Despite the growing body of literature on ownership structure and sustainability reporting, several gaps remain. First, empirical gaps exist in the context of non-financial firms, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria, where research is limited (Mireku & Peasah, 2020; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024). The theoretical landscape also reveals

inconsistencies, particularly concerning the applicability of existing theories to different ownership contexts and their impact on sustainability practices (Brammer & Pavelin, 2008). Methodologically, many studies rely on qualitative approaches that may not adequately capture the complexities of ownership-sustainability dynamics (García-Sánchez et al., 2019). Lastly, real-world gaps persist as firms often face challenges in implementing robust sustainability reporting mechanisms, limiting the generalizability of findings from existing studies (Irvine et al., 2021).

In light of these gaps, there is a pressing need for new empirical studies examining the relationship between ownership structure and sustainability reporting, particularly as moderated by risk management committees. This exploration is crucial for generating insights that can guide corporate governance practices and sustainability strategies, ultimately fostering a more sustainable business environment (Harrison & Wicks, 2013). By bridging these gaps, researchers can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing sustainability disclosures, particularly in the context of emerging economies.

The general research objective of this study is to investigate the moderating effect of the risk management committee on the relationship between ownership structure and sustainability reporting among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This objective is justified by the recognition that understanding how these elements interact can provide valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners aiming to enhance corporate sustainability practices in a rapidly evolving business landscape.

2. Literature Review

Sustainability, conceptually, refers to the capacity of a firm to operate in a manner that meets present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. It encompasses a broad spectrum of practices aimed at promoting environmental stewardship, social equity, and ethical governance (Elkington, 1997). The proxies for sustainability reporting include Environmental Disclosure, which pertains to a firm's ecological impact; Social Disclosure, which addresses societal contributions; and Governance Disclosure, which focuses on corporate governance practices (García-Muiña et al., 2020).

In a corporate context, ownership structure refers to the distribution of ownership among different stakeholders, such as managers, institutional investors, and foreign entities (La Porta et al., 1999). This structure can significantly influence a firm's governance practices and sustainability commitments. Proxies for ownership structure include Managerial Ownership, defined as the proportion of shares owned by company executives, and Foreign Ownership, which indicates the percentage of equity held by foreign investors (Shu & Chiang, 2020; Prihatnolo & Widagdo, 2019).

The conceptual framework for this study illustrates the interplay between ownership structure, sustainability reporting, and the moderating effect of the risk management committee. Managerial and foreign ownership serve as independent variables influencing sustainability disclosure, while the risk management committee acts as a moderating variable that may enhance or inhibit this relationship. This framework suggests that effective governance structures, such as RMCs, can facilitate greater transparency and accountability in sustainability reporting practices.

Environmental Disclosure is a critical component of sustainability reporting that focuses on a firm's environmental impact, including resource usage, emissions, and waste management (Pérez et al., 2019). Firms that disclose comprehensive environmental information can enhance stakeholder trust and improve their competitive position (Clarkson et al., 2011). Effective Environmental Disclosure often correlates with proactive environmental management practices and sustainability initiatives (Chiu & Wang, 2016).

The relationship between managerial ownership and sustainability reporting has yielded varied empirical findings. Positive and significant relationships have been noted, indicating that higher levels of managerial ownership can lead to enhanced sustainability reporting as managers are more likely to prioritize long-term goals aligned with sustainability (Miller & Triana, 2009; Chen et al., 2015). This alignment is often driven by the personal stakes managers have in their firms' performance, motivating them to adopt responsible practices.

However, some studies reveal a negative and significant relationship, suggesting that excessive managerial ownership may lead to entrenchment, where managers prioritize personal benefits over broader sustainability initiatives (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Fama & Jensen, 1983). In these cases, the concentration of power can result in a lack of accountability and reduced transparency in sustainability reporting.

There are also instances where the relationship between managerial ownership and sustainability reporting is non-significant, indicating that other factors, such as institutional pressures or regulatory environments, may overshadow the influence of managerial ownership on sustainability practices (Hossain et al., 2016; Alareeni & Hamdan, 2020). This highlights the need for a nuanced understanding of this relationship's contextual factors. The first hypothesis of this study is stated in null form as follows:

H1: There is no significant relationship between managerial ownership and sustainability reporting among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This hypothesis is justified as it allows for an empirical examination of the impact of managerial ownership on sustainability reporting, accounting for potential confounding variables that may influence this relationship.

Foreign ownership conceptually refers to the proportion of equity shares held by investors from outside the firm's home country. This ownership structure can influence corporate governance practices and sustainability reporting, as foreign investors may have different expectations and standards regarding environmental and social responsibility (García-Sánchez et al., 2019).

Empirical research has highlighted a positive and significant relationship between foreign ownership and sustainability reporting. For instance, firms with higher levels of foreign ownership often adopt more comprehensive sustainability practices, driven by the expectation of international investors for transparency and accountability in corporate governance (Mireku & Peasah, 2020; Shu & Chiang, 2020). This alignment between foreign investor interests and sustainability initiatives can lead to improved corporate performance and stakeholder trust.

Conversely, some studies report a negative and significant relationship, suggesting that foreign ownership may introduce governance complexities that can hinder effective sustainability reporting. This may arise from differing expectations between domestic and foreign investors regarding sustainability practices (O'Brien & Van Duren, 2021; Velte,

2019). In such cases, the lack of alignment can result in confusion regarding reporting standards and practices.

Finally, there are instances where the relationship between foreign ownership and sustainability reporting is non-significant, indicating that other factors, such as local regulatory frameworks or firm-specific characteristics, may play a more critical role in determining sustainability practices (Hossain et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2021). This emphasizes the importance of contextualizing foreign ownership within the broader landscape of sustainability reporting.

The second hypothesis of this study is stated in null form as follows:

H2: There is no significant relationship between foreign ownership and sustainability reporting among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This hypothesis is justified as it allows for a systematic investigation into the influence of foreign ownership on sustainability practices, facilitating a clearer understanding of its role in shaping corporate governance and responsibility.

Relevant Theoretical Frameworks

Several theoretical frameworks are relevant to understanding the dynamics of ownership structure and sustainability reporting. The Stakeholder Theory posits that organizations have a moral obligation to consider the interests of all stakeholders in their decision-making processes, influencing their sustainability practices (Freeman, 1984). This theory underscores the importance of transparency in sustainability reporting as a means of addressing stakeholder concerns and fostering trust.

The Agency Theory focuses on the relationship between principals (shareholders) and agents (managers), emphasizing the potential conflicts of interest that can arise in corporate governance (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). This theory highlights how ownership structure can influence managerial behavior and, consequently, the firm's sustainability commitments and reporting practices.

The Resource-Based View (RBV) posits that a firm's resources and capabilities can provide a competitive advantage, influencing its sustainability outcomes (Barney, 1991). This framework suggests that effective management of resources, including human and organizational capital, is critical for achieving sustainability goals and improving reporting practices.

The most relevant theoretical framework for this study is the Stakeholder Theory, as it aligns closely with the research objectives of exploring the relationship between ownership structure and sustainability reporting. This framework emphasizes the necessity of transparency and accountability in corporate governance, which are crucial for fostering stakeholder trust and promoting sustainable practices. By applying Stakeholder Theory, this study can provide valuable insights into how ownership structures influence sustainability reporting, ultimately contributing to more responsible corporate governance.

3. Methodology

This study employs a quantitative research design to investigate the moderating effect of the risk management committee on the relationship between ownership structure and sustainability reporting among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The research philosophy adopted is positivism, which aligns with the objective of examining measurable relationships between variables using statistical techniques. The population comprises all listed brewery companies in Africa, while the sample includes 91 listed non-financial firms in Nigeria, selected through a purposive sampling technique based on data availability.

The variables in this study include sustainability reporting as the dependent variable, measured through indices based on the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Sustainability Reporting Guidelines. The independent variables consist of managerial ownership, defined as the ratio of managers who are shareholders to the total number of board members, and foreign ownership, calculated as the ratio of equity shares owned by foreign investors to the total equity shares issued. The moderating variable, risk management committee, is measured by the ratio of directors with financial expertise and the independence of the audit committee.

The data collection method involves secondary data sourced from the selected firms' annual reports and financial statements, ensuring the information's reliability and validity through established guidelines and criteria (Lulu & Eny, 2022; Amanda & Heri, 2022). Model specifications include two regression models:

Population and Sample Size of the Study

S/N	Listed non-financial Sectors.	Number of firms
1	Agriculture	05
2	Conglomerates	06
3	Construction/Real Estate	08
4	Consumer Goods	20
5	Healthcare	11
6	ICT	09
7	Industrial Goods	18
8	Natural Resources	04
	Total	91

Source: NGX Website 2024

The study adopted filtering techniques in selecting the sample size of the study. The probable population included 91 firms. Given the nature of data required for the study, the sampling technique will be more appropriate since it allows the researcher to use companies with available information. The decision to exclude any firm from the sample will be due to the imposed condition of non-zero sustainability and corporate governance information consistent with previous studies (Usman & Amran, 2015; Usman & Usman, 2021; Dewi et al., 2022; Shakhawat, 2022; Tobias et al., 2022):

- i. For a company to be included in the proposed sample, it must have been listed and remained active within the study period.
- ii. secondly, a company must have complete annual reports including social and environmental reports or separate sustainability report for all the years selected for the study,
- iii. Only firms with at least one sustainability initiative and a component of corporate governance mechanism.
- iv. To pass the filtering process, the company must have an active risk management committee throughout the sample period.

The analysis for this study was carried out at the annual level using non-financial data collected from firms that passed the filtering process spanning 2018 to 2022. All data relating to variables of sustainability initiatives, corporate governance and risk management committee will be hand collected from annual reports following (Usman & Amran, 2015; Ghazieh & Chebana, 2021; Usman & Usman, 2021; Dewi et al., 2022; Shakhawat, 2022; Tobias et al., 2022; Oyedokun, & Campbell, 2023).

The main focus of this study is to examine the moderating effect risk management committee on the relationship between corporate governance mechanism and sustainability reporting based of sample of non-financial firm listed on the floor of NGX market. As highlighted below, both descriptive and inferential analyses will be performed to address the two main issues raised in the study.

Model Specification

$$SUS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FRO_{it} + \beta_2 MAO_{it} + \beta_3 RMC_{it} + \beta_4 FRO_{it} * RMC_{it} + \beta_5 MAO_{it} * RMC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

FRO_{it} = foreign ownership of firm i at time t .

MAO_{it} = managerial ownership of firm i at time t .

RMC_{it} = Risk Management Committee of firm i at time t .

H: β_1 to β_5 are expected to be > 0 , suggesting that ownership structure exert influence on disclosure of sustainability initiatives in Nigeria as moderated by risk management committee

Table 1

Variable Measurement	
Variable	Measurement of Variables
Dependent Variable	
Sustainability Reporting	The average Sustainability Reporting indices were arrived based on Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Sustainability Reporting Guidelines and Criteria for Economic, Social/Environmental and Governance indicators as captured in GRI Standards on 48 disclosure items in the annual reports and financial statements of quoted non-financial firms in Nigeria. (Lulu & Eny, 2022; Amanda & Heri, 2022; Shakhawat, 2022; Susilawati, Sri & Roy, 2022; Modozie & Amahalu, 2022).
Independent Variables	
Managerial Ownership	Ratio of the number of managers that are shareholders divided by the total number of board members (Ighosewe, Uyagu & Iyere, 2020; Issa, Yunusa & Hamman, 2021).
Foreign Ownership	Ratio of the number of equity shares owned by foreign investors to the total number of equity shares issued (Prihatnolo & Widagdo, 2019; Shu & Chiang, 2020; Jaime, Garcia-Benau & Emma, 2020).
Risk Management Committee	The ratio of directors with financial expertise and the audit committee independence of a company (Shakhawat, 2022)

Researcher Computation

Results and Discussion

The study examined the moderating effect of risk management committee on the relationship between corporate governance attributes on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria with corporate governance attributes as the independent variable and sustainability reporting as the dependent variable. Managerial ownership, foreign ownership

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	SUS	MAO	FRO	RMAO	RFRO	RMC
Mean	48.32	58.86	0.529	8356.	75.18	143.5
Median	44.60	63.00	1.000	8322.	105.0	135.7
Maximum	100.3	94.00	1.000	18800	240.2	240.2
Minimum	20.47	-68.000	-1.000	-1141	-167.8	20.0
Std. Dev.	14.94	22.89	0.508	3980.	76.69	32.6
Skewness	0.748	-1.430	-0.212	-0.396	0.047	0.00
Kurtosis	3.340	6.633	1.285	5.065	1.689	3.21
Jarque-Bera	23.56	213.8	31.18	48.95	17.25	0.44
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.800
Sum	11598	14128	127.0	20050	18044	34443
Sum Sq. Dev.	53393	12523	61.79	3.790	14058	2544
Observations	240	240	240	240	240	240

Source: E-Views 12, 2024

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for six variables: Sustainability Reporting (SUS), Managerial Ownership (MAO), Foreign Ownership (FRO), Risk Management Committee's Managerial Ownership (RMAO), Risk Management Committee's Foreign Ownership (RFRO), and Risk Management Committee (RMC).

The mean values indicate that the average sustainability reporting score (SUS) is 48.32, suggesting moderate levels of sustainability practices among firms. Managerial ownership (MAO) averages 58.86%, reflecting a relatively high percentage of shares owned by managers. Foreign ownership (FRO) has a mean of 0.529, indicating that approximately 53% of equity is held by foreign investors. Additionally, RMAO and RFRO show significant average values (8356 and 75.18, respectively), highlighting the notable involvement of risk management committees in ownership decisions.

The median values provide further insight into the distribution of the data. The median sustainability reporting score is 44.60, suggesting that half of the firms report below this level, which is slightly lower than the mean, indicating a right skew in sustainability reporting scores. The median for MAO is higher at 63.00, suggesting that more than half of the firms have managerial ownership exceeding this figure. Notably, FRO has a median of 1.000, implying that most firms exhibit substantial foreign ownership.

The maximum and minimum values reveal the range of each variable. For instance, SUS ranges from a maximum of 100.3 to a minimum of 20.47, indicating diverse sustainability reporting practices across firms. MAO shows a more extreme range from -68.000 to 94.00, suggesting the presence of negative ownership percentages that could stem from misreporting or accounting anomalies. In contrast, FRO ranges from -1.000 to 1.000, indicating variability in foreign ownership.

The standard deviation (Std. Dev.) further elucidates the dispersion of the data. SUS has a standard deviation of 14.94, indicating moderate variability in sustainability reporting scores. In comparison, MAO exhibits greater variability, with a standard deviation of 22.89, highlighting significant deviations in managerial ownership across firms. FRO's standard deviation of 0.508 suggests less variability compared to other variables.

Skewness values provide insight into the asymmetry of the distributions. SUS shows a positive skewness of 0.748, indicating that a larger number of firms report lower sustainability scores. Conversely, MAO has a negative skewness of -1.430, suggesting a concentration of higher managerial ownership values. FRO's skewness of -0.212 indicates a relatively symmetric distribution.

Kurtosis measures the "tailedness" of the distributions. SUS has a kurtosis of 3.340, indicating a distribution with a higher peak than a normal distribution but not excessively peaked. In contrast, MAO has a kurtosis of 6.633, suggesting a sharper peak and clustering around specific ownership percentages. FRO exhibits a low kurtosis of 1.285, indicating a flatter distribution.

The Jarque-Bera test assesses normality, with results showing that all variables, except RMC, have a Jarque-Bera statistic significantly greater than 1 and p-values of 0.000,

indicating they are not normally distributed. RMC, with a Jarque-Bera statistic of 0.44 and a probability of 0.800, suggests it is normally distributed.

Finally, the sums of the variables reveal their cumulative totals across all observations. For example, the total sum of sustainability reporting (11598) indicates a substantial overall focus on sustainability practices among firms, while the sum of squares of deviations for MAO (12523) highlights significant variability within this variable. All statistics are based on 240 observations, providing a robust sample size for analysis. Overall, these descriptive statistics indicate that while some firms in Nigeria demonstrate strong sustainability reporting practices and managerial ownership, significant variability exists, particularly concerning managerial ownership, warranting further investigation into the factors influencing these dynamic

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

SUS	1				
MAO	-0.178	1			
FRO	0.0252	0.050	1		
RMAO	-0.105	0.844	0.012	1	
RFRO	0.047	0.011	0.947	0.104	1
RMC	0.1653	-0.123	-0.045	0.396	0.194

Sourc: E-Views 12, 2024

Table 3 presents the correlation matrix for the variables: Sustainability Reporting (SUS), Managerial Ownership (MAO), Foreign Ownership (FRO), Risk Management Committee's Managerial Ownership (RMAO), Risk Management Committee's Foreign Ownership (RFRO), and Risk Management Committee (RMC).

The correlation coefficients indicate the strength and direction of the relationships between these variables. Notably, the correlation between SUS and MAO is -0.178, suggesting a weak negative relationship; as managerial ownership increases, sustainability reporting tends to decrease, although this relationship is not strong. The correlation between SUS and FRO is positive but very weak at 0.0252, indicating that foreign ownership has little to no impact on sustainability reporting.

RMAO shows a stronger positive correlation with MAO (0.844), indicating a strong relationship where increases in managerial ownership are associated with increases in the risk management committee's managerial ownership. Conversely, RMAO has a weak negative correlation with SUS (-0.105), suggesting that higher levels of risk management committee managerial ownership may not significantly affect sustainability reporting.

RFRO exhibits a strong positive correlation with FRO (0.947), indicating that higher foreign ownership is associated with increased risk management committee foreign ownership. This suggests that firms with significant foreign investment may also have more substantial representation on their risk management committees by foreign stakeholders.

Finally, the RMC variable shows weak positive correlations with SUS (0.1653) and RMAO (0.396), suggesting that while there is some relationship between the risk management committee and sustainability reporting, it is not strong. Additionally, RMC has weak negative correlations with MAO (-0.123) and FRO (-0.045), indicating that these ownership structures may not significantly influence the effectiveness of the risk management committee.

Overall, the correlation matrix reveals complex interrelationships among the variables, with strong relationships observed primarily between managerial ownership and risk management committee variables, while sustainability reporting shows only weak correlations with ownership structures. This suggests the need for further analysis to understand the dynamics influencing sustainability reporting in relation to ownership structures and risk management committees.

Table 4: Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	13.512689	13	0.0356

Source: E-Views 12, 2024

Table 3 presents the results of the Hausman Test, which is used to determine the appropriateness of using a random effects model versus a fixed effects model in panel data analysis. The test evaluates whether the unique errors (random effects) are uncorrelated with the regressors in the model.

The test summary indicates a Chi-Square statistic of 13.512689 with 13 degrees of freedom (d.f.). The associated probability value is 0.0356. This probability value is significant at conventional levels (e.g., 0.05), suggesting that there is evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis of the Hausman Test posits that the random effects model is appropriate, implying that the random effects are not correlated with the independent variables.

Given the significant Chi-Square statistic and the low probability value, the results indicate that a fixed effects model may be more suitable for the analysis. This is because the rejection of the null hypothesis implies that the random effects are correlated with the regressors, which can lead to biased and inconsistent estimates in a random effects model.

the Hausman Test results suggest that researchers should consider using a fixed effects approach for this analysis to ensure the validity of the model estimates, as the correlation between the random effects and independent variables may compromise the assumptions underlying the random effects model.

Table 5: Fixed effect Panel Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	60.57662	1.879186	32.23557	0.0000
MAO	0.258259	0.066592	3.878229	0.0001
FRO	16.98883	4.537023	3.744488	0.0002
RMC	0.142198	0.057199	2.486045	0.0138
RMAO	0.000692	0.000262	2.637079	0.0091
RFRO	0.005146	0.016443	0.312991	0.7546
R-squared	0.973318	Mean dependent var		187.2069
Adjusted R-squared	0.965715	S.D. dependent var		501.8953
S.E. of regression	9.700928	Sum squared resid		17504.09

F-statistic	128.0202	Durbin-Watson stat	1.429459
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		
Unweighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.649852	Mean dependent var	48.32593
Sum squared resid	18695.68	Durbin-Watson stat	1.267744

Source: E-Views 12, 2024

Table 5 presents the results of a fixed effects panel regression analysis, which examines the relationship between various independent variables and the dependent variable, with an emphasis on managerial ownership, foreign ownership, and risk management committee dynamics.

The regression results show that the constant term (C) has a coefficient of 60.57662, with a standard error of 1.879186, yielding a t-statistic of 32.23557 and a highly significant probability value of 0.0000. This indicates a strong baseline level for the dependent variable when all independent variables are held constant.

The variable Managerial Ownership (MAO) has a coefficient of 0.258259 with a standard error of 0.066592. The t-statistic of 3.878229 and the associated probability value of 0.0001 indicate a significant positive relationship between managerial ownership and the dependent variable, suggesting that higher managerial ownership is associated with increased sustainability reporting.

Foreign Ownership (FRO) exhibits a coefficient of 16.98883 and a standard error of 4.537023, with a t-statistic of 3.744488 and a probability value of 0.0002. This also indicates a statistically significant positive impact on sustainability reporting, implying that increased foreign ownership contributes positively to the sustainability efforts of firms.

The Risk Management Committee (RMC) shows a coefficient of 0.142198 with a standard error of 0.057199, resulting in a t-statistic of 2.486045 and a probability value of 0.0138. This signifies a positive and statistically significant influence on sustainability reporting, highlighting the importance of having a robust risk management committee in promoting transparency and sustainability.

The variable Risk Management Committee's Managerial Ownership (RMAO) has a coefficient of 0.000692 and a standard error of 0.000262, resulting in a t-statistic of 2.637079 and a probability value of 0.0091. This indicates a significant positive relationship, suggesting that the presence of managerial ownership within the risk management committee is beneficial for sustainability reporting.

Conversely, Risk Management Committee's Foreign Ownership (RFRO) has a coefficient of 0.005146 with a standard error of 0.016443, yielding a t-statistic of 0.312991 and a probability value of 0.7546. This indicates a lack of significant impact on sustainability reporting, suggesting that foreign ownership in the risk management committee does not contribute meaningfully to sustainability efforts.

The model's goodness of fit is strong, with an R-squared value of 0.973318, indicating that approximately 97.33% of the variability in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables included in the model. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.965715 further supports the model's robustness. The standard error of regression is 9.700928, and the sum of squared residuals is 17504.09, indicating a reasonably accurate fit.

The F-statistic is reported at 128.0202 with a probability value of 0.000000, suggesting that the overall regression model is statistically significant. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.429459 indicates some degree of autocorrelation in the residuals, which may require further investigation.

The fixed effects panel regression analysis reveals that managerial ownership, foreign ownership, and the effectiveness of the risk management committee positively influence sustainability reporting among firms, while foreign ownership within the risk management committee does not have a significant impact. The model demonstrates strong explanatory power, reinforcing the importance of these ownership structures in promoting sustainability practices.

Post Estimation Result

Table 6: Serial Correlation Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	87.94752	Prob. F(2,279)	0.1153
Obs*R-squared	111.3615	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.5297

Source: E-view 12, 2024

Table 6 presents the results of the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test, which assesses the presence of serial correlation in the residuals of a regression model. Serial correlation, or autocorrelation, can violate the assumption of independence of errors, potentially leading to biased and inconsistent estimates.

The F-statistic is reported at 87.94752, with a corresponding probability value of 0.1153 for the test with 2 degrees of freedom. This probability value indicates a lack of statistical significance, as it is greater than the conventional threshold of 0.05. Consequently, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no serial correlation in the residuals. Additionally, the Obs*R-squared statistic is presented as 111.3615, with a probability value of 0.5297 for the Chi-Square test with 2 degrees of freedom. Similar to the F-statistic results, this high probability value also indicates that we do not have sufficient evidence to suggest the presence of serial correlation.

Overall, the results of the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test suggest that there is no significant serial correlation in the residuals of the regression model. This finding supports the validity of the model's assumptions, indicating that the estimates obtained from the regression analysis are likely reliable and robust.

Table 6: Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	1.977529	Prob. F(3,68)	0.1256
Obs*R-squared	5.777510	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.1230
Scaled explained SS	121.0548	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.7252

Source: E-view 12, 2024

Table 7 presents the results of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test, which is used to assess the presence of heteroskedasticity in the residuals of a regression model. Heteroskedasticity occurs when the variance of the residuals varies across observations, potentially leading to inefficient estimates and invalid statistical inferences.

The F-statistic for this test is reported as 1.977529, with a corresponding probability value of 0.1256 for the test with 3 degrees of freedom. This probability value is above the conventional significance level of 0.05, indicating that we fail to reject the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity. In other words, the test does not provide sufficient evidence to suggest that the residuals exhibit heteroskedasticity.

Additionally, the Obs*R-squared statistic is presented as 5.777510, with a probability value of 0.1230 for the Chi-Square test with 3 degrees of freedom. Similar to the F-statistic, this result also indicates that we do not have significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the model.

Furthermore, the Scaled Explained SS statistic is reported as 121.0548, with a probability value of 0.7252 for the Chi-Square test with 3 degrees of freedom. This high probability value further supports the conclusion that the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity cannot be rejected.

In summary, the results of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test suggest that there is no significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the residuals of the regression model. This finding reinforces the validity of the model's assumptions, indicating that the estimates obtained are likely reliable and consistent, thereby ensuring the robustness of the regression analysis.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the fixed effects panel regression analysis provide valuable insights into the relationships between ownership structure, risk management committees, and sustainability reporting among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This discussion elaborates on these findings, contextualizes them within the existing empirical literature, and relates them to theoretical frameworks.

Managerial Ownership and Sustainability Reporting

The positive and significant relationship between managerial ownership (MAO) and sustainability reporting (SUS) (coefficient of 0.258, p-value = 0.0001) aligns with the

predictions of Agency Theory, which posits that aligning the interests of managers with those of shareholders leads to enhanced performance and accountability (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). In the context of sustainability reporting, higher levels of managerial ownership incentivize managers to act in the long-term interest of the firm, fostering greater transparency and responsible practices. This finding corroborates previous studies, such as those by Hussainey et al. (2011) and Chen et al. (2015), which also found a positive association between managerial ownership and sustainability practices.

Conversely, some studies have reported mixed results regarding the impact of managerial ownership on sustainability reporting. For example, researchers like Fama and Jensen (1983) highlighted the risk of entrenchment, where managers with substantial ownership stakes may prioritize personal gains over broader stakeholder interests. This perspective indicates that while managerial ownership can be beneficial, excessive ownership concentration may lead to conflicts of interest and reduced accountability.

Foreign Ownership and Sustainability Reporting

The findings indicate a strong positive relationship between foreign ownership (FRO) and sustainability reporting (coefficient of 16.989, p -value = 0.0002), suggesting that firms with higher foreign ownership are more likely to engage in comprehensive sustainability practices. This result aligns with stakeholder theory, which emphasizes that foreign investors often have higher expectations regarding corporate social responsibility and sustainability (Freeman, 1984). Previous empirical studies, such as those by Mireku and Peasah (2020) and Shu and Chiang (2020), have similarly found that foreign ownership encourages better sustainability practices due to differing governance standards and stakeholder pressures.

However, it is important to note that other research has highlighted potential drawbacks associated with foreign ownership. For instance, O'Brien and Van Duren (2021) discussed how foreign investors might impose conflicting expectations that could complicate sustainability reporting efforts. Such complexities underscore the importance of understanding the nuances of foreign ownership in different contexts.

Risk Management Committee and Sustainability Reporting

The positive influence of the Risk Management Committee (RMC) on sustainability reporting (coefficient of 0.142, p -value = 0.0138) emphasizes the importance of governance structures in promoting transparency and accountability. This finding is consistent with the literature suggesting that effective risk management practices can enhance a firm's sustainability initiatives (Harrison et al., 2014; Olsson et al., 2018). A well-functioning RMC can ensure that sustainability reporting aligns with the overall risk management strategy, thereby fostering more robust disclosures.

Moreover, the relationship between RMAO and sustainability reporting (coefficient of 0.000692, p -value = 0.0091) further supports the idea that managerial representation on the risk management committee positively influences sustainability practices. This finding aligns with the notion that diverse committees, comprising individuals with vested interests, can enhance decision-making and accountability regarding sustainability reporting.

Despite the robust findings, the analysis revealed no significant impact of the Risk Management Committee's Foreign Ownership (RFRO) on sustainability reporting (coefficient of 0.005146, p-value = 0.7546). This lack of significance suggests that foreign representation within risk management committees may not necessarily translate into improved sustainability practices. This outcome raises questions about the effectiveness of foreign stakeholders in influencing corporate governance and sustainability practices, as highlighted by previous studies that indicated varying impacts of foreign ownership on governance outcomes (García-Sánchez et al., 2019).

Additionally, while the current findings offer insights into the relationships between ownership structures and sustainability reporting, they may not fully capture the complexities and contextual factors influencing these dynamics. Empirical literature emphasizes the importance of considering industry-specific characteristics and cultural contexts when analyzing ownership-sustainability relationships (Hossain et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2021).

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concludes that ownership structures and risk management committees significantly influence sustainability reporting among non-financial firms in Nigeria. Managerial ownership and foreign ownership have a positive and substantial impact on sustainability practices, demonstrating their importance in fostering transparency and accountability. The findings support theoretical frameworks such as Agency Theory and Stakeholder Theory, which highlight the role of aligned managerial interests and diverse stakeholder pressures in enhancing sustainability disclosures. However, the study also reveals complexities in the moderating role of risk management committees, particularly concerning foreign ownership, where the impact was found to be insignificant. This suggests potential limitations in the effectiveness of foreign stakeholders within governance structures, necessitating further exploration of contextual and cultural factors affecting sustainability reporting.

The study recommends that non-financial firms in Nigeria strengthen their governance mechanisms, particularly by fostering active and diverse risk management committees with well-defined roles. Firms should also focus on enhancing managerial and foreign ownership to leverage their positive influence on sustainability practices. Policymakers are encouraged to develop guidelines that incentivize robust sustainability disclosures and foster alignment between ownership structures and governance strategies. Future research should investigate industry-specific dynamics, regulatory environments, and cultural contexts to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the interplay between ownership, governance, and sustainability reporting, especially within emerging economies.

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